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DIVERSE FORMS DESIGN BASED ON CONCEPTS OF EMERGENT DESIGN AND OPTIMUM DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the concepts of emergent design and optimum design, which are types of artifact design. Emergent design has interactivity between bottom-up and top-down processes, whereas optimum design is a top-down process only. Hence, emergent design is applicable to design problems requiring a global solution search and derivation of diverse solutions when design objectives and conditions are unclear. In contrast, optimum design is applicable to design problems requiring a local solution search and derivation of a unique optimal solution when design objectives and conditions are clear. Moreover, we propose an emergent design system based on multiple iterations of the bottom-up and top-down processes. The multiple iteration system can derive design solutions that are similar to the design solution derived upon of the first iteration using the emergent design system.

Keywords: Emergent Design, Optimum Design, Emergence

Introduction

The design process can be roughly divided into two categories: the early process and the late process. These processes have different features. The early process consists of conceptual and basic designs. Additionally, diverse design candidates must be obtained from a global solution search under unclear design conditions using the designer's experience and knowledge. In contrast, the late process consists of detailed design where a unique solution is derived using an optimization method, which is an engineering design method with clear objectives and conditions. Currently the method to derive diverse design solution candidates in the early process is

trial-and-error. Consequently, the design solution depends on the designer's experience and knowledge, and obtaining a localized solution is possible. Therefore, a method to search for a global solution is needed (Matsuoka (2010)).

In this research, the concepts of emergent design and optimum design, which are types of artifact design, are demonstrated. First, we explain the concept of "emergence", including phenomena in nature, and its relation to "emergent design". Then conditions and design problems for emergent design and optimum design are investigated. Moreover, we propose an emergent design system based on multiple iterations of the bottom-up and top-down processes in emergent design, and demonstrate diverse design solutions are derived using this system.

CONCEPT OF EMERGENCE

EMERGENCE

In nature, various organisms exist in the same environment. In the fields of biology and ecology, scientists have hypothesized that these species are created through the process of emergence. Kitamura (Kitamura, 1995) defines emergence as a new function, character, and action acquired by an interactive dynamic process where global order appears through local interactions between individuals behaving autonomously with the environment. However, this order restrains the behavior of an individual. Thus, the appearance of global order is a bottom-up process, whereas the process of restraining individual behavior is a top-down process (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Concept of Emergence

EMERGENCE PHENOMENON IN NATURE

In organic systems, autonomous behavior of the elements has been indicated for a certain function to appear. An example of a specific emergence phenomenon is flocking birds (Fig. 2) (Reynolds, 1987). When birds fly in a flock, each individual determines its own speed and direction of flight while observing the actions of the birds in its immediate vicinity. If they fly too close, they collide; too far apart, and they break away. Consequently, the birds fly and maintain appropriate intervals. In this case, the structural elements are the birds and the reciprocal behaviors are collision avoidance, speed adjustment, and centripetal force to keep from breaking away from the flock. This local interaction of structural elements generates large-scale order of the flock as a whole, and is reflected in the flying patterns of each bird.

EMERGENT DESIGN AND OPTIMUM DESIGN

SIMILARITIES BETWEEN DESIGN AND EMERGENCE

Design can be roughly divided into the early process and the late process. The features of these processes differ. The early process focuses on “conceptual design” and “basic design”, which are used for the design concept and objective, and basic specifications and structure, respectively. In the late process, the concept and basic specifications determined in the early process are used to perform

Fig. 2 Flocking Birds

a “detailed design” to determine specific details such as component materials and dimensions. During the early process, the design objectives and constraining conditions are not established; therefore, diverse design solution candidates are sought from a wide solution space. Consequently, a vast heuristic search is performed for complex, non-linear multimodal problems and problems between different topologies. Normally at this stage, designers and planners employ their intuition and experience in a trial-and-error process to deduce diverse design solution candidates. The distinguishing feature of early design is that the process corresponds to the reciprocal interaction of the bottom-up and top-down processes seen in emergence. Moreover, design solution candidates deduced in the early process along with the clarified design objectives and constraining conditions are then used in the late process to optimize a somewhat limited solution space. Therefore, a local solution search for simple unimodal problems and problems between the same topology is conducted. In this solution search, the focus becomes a top-down optimization of each component from the overall design solution candidates obtained in the early process. Although the process, which corresponds to the reciprocal interaction in emergence, exists, compared to the early process, the role of the bottom-up process is relatively small and highly dependent on the top-down process.

	Emergent Design		Optimum Design
	Bottom-up Process	Top-down Process	
Design Objective	Unclear	Clear	Clear
Restriction Condition	Unclear	Clear	Clear
Design Solution	New, Diverse Solution Candidates	New, Diverse Solutions	Unique Solution

Table 1 Comparison of Feature of Design Method

The emergent phenomenon and the early design process have many similarities. Like emergence, design solution candidates are initially extracted for design objectives and constraint conditions, which are not yet established. In other words, design solution candidates seem to occur by coincidence in the early process. Hence, the process where diverse design solution candidates manifest themselves is essentially the same as the coexistence of bottom-up and top-down processes in the emergent process. At the same time, the process where detailed portions of the design solution candidate are optimized in the late process is similar to the emergent process where the structural elements are constrained by the overall features in the top-down process. In this way, the basic characteristics of design and phenomenon are similar, especially in the early design process. Thus, the potential of emergent concepts in design is thought-provoking.

EMERGENT DESIGN

As the design process moves from the early to late process, the design objectives and conditions gradually become clear. Additionally, the preferred design method changes as the design in the early and late processes has different characteristics. In the early process, “emergent design”, which has bottom-up and top-down processes in reciprocal interactions, is performed. Table 1 shows the features of emergent design where emergent design is a bottom-up manifestation of possible design solution candidates with unclear design objectives and constraining conditions, while the top-down optimization is a reciprocal interactive process. Through multiple iterations of this interactive

process, new and diverse design solution candidates are produced (Fig. 3(a)).

Figure 4 illustrates the structure of emergent design with a reciprocal feature and a design method inclusive of the early and late processes. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the bottom-up process of emergent design creates design solution candidates through the interaction between structural elements in the emergent process. Normally, it is difficult to establish design conditions in the early design process. Hence, a wide-ranging solution search is necessary to generate new and diverse design solution candidates using a general evaluation standard. In the top-down process, structural elements of the design solution candidates generated in the bottom-up process are regulated to produce a design solution. Using the design objectives and constraining conditions established in the top-down process and numerous iterations to refine the details, the various design solution candidates obtained in bottom-up process are optimized. As shown in Fig.

Fig. 3 Emergent Design and Optimum Design

4(b), element optimization is performed with minimal modifications of the relationship between elements as possible. In this manner emergent design produces new design solutions while maintaining the diversity of the solutions from the bottom-up process.

OPTIMUM DESIGN

Optimum design determines the best design solution using the relationship between the objective function and constraint conditions under specific design conditions. First, an assumed design problem is broken down to extract design variables. Next, the constraint conditions of each extracted design variable are clarified. Then objective functions, which depict the relationship between the design objective and design variables, are determined using the design variables. Moreover, conditions to determine the design solution are clarified; the objective function is minimized or maximized. Finally, the optimum design solution is obtained by the relationship between the objective function and constraint conditions, which expresses the design objective.

Optimum design derives a unique optimum design solution using the aforementioned procedure. Moreover, optimum design derives part from the whole, similar to Fig. 3(b). When a design problem assumes the whole, the optimum design solution is finally derived for the extracted design variables by breaking down this whole. For this reason, this design solution corresponds to only part of the whole. Hence, optimum design is a top-down design method,

Fig. 4 Emergent Design

which derives the part from the whole by considering the whole-part relationship. Table 1 lists the features of optimum design. Unlike emergent design, which derives diverse design solution candidates, optimum design derives a unique design solution (Table 1).

EMERGENT DESIGN SYSTEM

OUTLINE OF EMERGENT DESIGN SYSTEM

Figure 5 shows the emergent design system based on the emergent design. The emergent design system consists of bottom-up process and top-down process. In bottom-up process, diverse solution candidates meeting the low standard set by the designer are derived, while the top-down process satisfies the constraint conditions, and optimizes candidates that satisfy the constraints. This system derives diverse solutions by going through these two processes.

BOTTOM-UP PROCESS

In the bottom-up process, forms are generated self-organizationally using cellular automata (CA). In this method, the states of cells in the lattice are updated

Fig. 5 Emergent Design System

according to a local rule (Oda J., Kundu S., and Koishi T, 1994). More specifically, at time t , the state of an element is S_t and the state of the neighborhood is N_t . Equation (1) describes the state of the element S_{t+1} at time $t+1$

$$S_{t+1} = f(S_t, N_t) \quad (1)$$

where f is the transition function, which influences the behaviors of the elements. Many form-generation methods using CA have been proposed (Cao YJ., 1998, Gandin Ch-A., 1999). In this study, the diversity of an organism is noted, and rules referring to two properties for diverse organism morphogenesis, ‘induction’ and ‘apical dominance’, are the input vectors for the CA (Shiokawa, K. 1991, Nakagawa, S. 1975).

An organism is formed by interactions between neighborhood cells. These neighborhood cells affect a cell, causing a cell to change and exhibit different features (Fig. 6(a)). This property is called ‘induction’. The first input is defined as the neighborhood information vector \mathbf{v}_n , which is expressed by Eq. (2).

$$\mathbf{v}_n = \sum_{i=1}^{26} b_i w_i \mathbf{e}_n \quad (2)$$

Where i is the surrounding element number, b_i indicates the existence or non-existence of an element (1 or 0, respectively), w_i is the coefficient of the vector direction, and \mathbf{e}_i is the unit vector of the direction to the object element.

In the developmental process, a certain tissue dominates, such as the bud of a plant or the head of an animal. Such tissues are called the apex, and the dominant action by the apex is called ‘apical dominance’ (Fig. 6(b)). The second input is defined as the positional information vector \mathbf{v}_p , which is expressed by Eq. (3).

$$\mathbf{v}_p = (d_{\max} - d) \mathbf{e}_d \quad (3)$$

Where d_{\max} is the distance between the apex and the most distant cell from the apex, d is the distance between the apex and the object element, and \mathbf{e}_d is the unit vector of the direction to the object element. Moreover, the composite ratio k is set and input vector \mathbf{v}_{in} is defined as expressed in Eq. (4).

$$\mathbf{v}_{in} = k\mathbf{v}_n + (1-k)\mathbf{v}_p \quad (4)$$

(a) Induction

(b) Apical Dominance

Fig. 6 Model of the Input Vector

Diverse forms can be generated by changing the composite ratio k . Thus, diverse design solution candidates are generated self-organizationally in the bottom-up process.

TOP-DOWN PROCESS

In the top-down process, diverse forms are modified to satisfy design constraints such as strength. In this system, modifications are inspired by an adaptive function of bone remodeling. First, stress on the design solution candidate is calculated via the finite element method (Fig. 7(a)), and then stress evaluations are conducted on surface elements that compose the design solution candidate (Fig. 7(b)). During the evaluation, the elements are increased or decreased by comparing the stress σ_i in the object element and the feasible stress σ_c . If the stress σ_i in the object element is lower than the feasible stress σ_c , the object element is deleted (Fig. 7(b-1)). However, if the stress σ_i in the object element is higher than the feasible stress σ_c , a new element is added on the opposite side of the surrounding element (Fig. 7(b-2)). The elements are increased or decreased until they reach the trial number, which the designer sets (Fig. 7(c)). Each design solution

Fig. 7 Increasing and Decreasing Elements by Modification Method

candidate derived in the bottom-up process is modified using this method to derive diverse design solutions that satisfy the feasible stress.

APPLICATION TO CANTILEVER BEAM DESIGN

In this section, we show the effectiveness of deriving diverse design solutions by applying the proposed system to a two-dimensional cantilever beam design.

Fig. 8 Input Conditions in Bottom-up Process

EXECUTION RESULT OF BOTTOM-UP PROCESS

Figure 8 shows the input conditions to generate a two-dimensional cantilever beam. The generation space and quad element are set to 150 × 75. The initial elements are set on the left side and middle point of right side where a load is applied. Apexes are set on the upper and lower points of the right side. In addition, there are two evaluation points: the initial elements are joined at least one point and the number of elements is at least 2250. Based on these conditions, 600 design solution candidates are derived.

Fig. 9 Form Generation Process

Figure 9 depicts the generation process. Each initial element grows self-organizingly, and one form is generated. Additionally, Fig. 10 shows examples of design solution candidates generated in the bottom-up process where the shape features have liner holes, lack elements, have mesh structures, etc. These figures confirm that the emergent design system can derive diverse design solution candidates in the bottom-up process.

Fig. 10 Examples of Solution Candidates

EXECUTION RESULT OF TOP-DOWN PROCESS

The top-down process is conducted for the 600 design solution candidates generated in the bottom-up process. 533 design solutions satisfy the constraint conditions as a feasible solution. A

Fig. 11 Stress Distribution of Diverse Solution Candidates After Increasing and Decreasing Elements

feasible solution is a solution that satisfies the strength. Figure 11 shows an example of the modification process in the top-down process. The design solution candidate in Fig. 11(a) where the thin left side is restrained to the wall shows a high stress value. Additionally, some tiny holes appear on the right side where a load is applied. However, when the number of iterations is 10, the left side becomes thick by increasing the elements, and the stress value decreases. Moreover, the tiny holes disappear due to the increase in the elements, and when the number of iterations is 40, the tiny holes located on the right side where stress value is low disappear completely. Large holes, which are seen in the design solution candidates, remain after the modification.

The design solution candidate in Fig. 11(b) has elements mainly in the upper and lower-left parts. However, when the number of iteration is 10, the elements at lower-left parts where the stress value is low decrease. When the number of iterations is 50, these elements disappear completely, and the tiny holes in the upper parts become large due to the decrease in the elements. Design solution (b) has elements mainly in the upper parts. The characteristic is also seen in design solution candidate (b). Because form characteristics are reflected after the modification, the design solution candidates are strengthened by increasing and decreasing elements while maintaining the original

form characteristics. Figure 12 shows other design solutions. There are shape features with liner holes, sharp-set, tiny holes, etc. Thus, diverse design solutions that satisfy the design objectives and constraint conditions are derived by the bottom-up process and the top-down process.

ITERATING THE BOTTOM-UP AND TOP-DOWN PROCESSES

We attempted to repeat the interactive dynamic processes in the emergent design system. Originally, reiterating the dynamic bottom-up and top-down processes in emergent design was believed to produce novelty and diversity. Therefore, it can be inferred that multiple iterations of the bottom-up and top-down processes should increase diversity. Figure 13 shows the results of applying these processes to two-dimensional cantilever beams in the emergent design system. Figure 13(a) shows the design solution candidates generated based on design solution A, which is derived initially in the top-down process, while Fig. 13(b) depicts these design solution candidates modified in the top-down process. The design solutions derived in the top-down process are similar to design solution A, which has a triangular structure. Therefore, it can be inferred that repeating of the bottom-up and the top-down processes can derive design solutions that are similar to the design solutions derived using the top-down process only once.

Fig. 12 Examples of Solutions Derived from Fig. 10 by Using Modification Method

CONCLUSIONS

The concepts of emergent design and optimum design, which are artifact designs applicable to the early and late design processes, are discussed. We propose a system based on emergent design. The results are summarized as:

- 1) Emergent design has a reciprocal interactive process, and is applicable to derive diverse design solution candidates where the design objectives and constraint conditions are unclear.
- 2) Optimum design is a top-down method to derive part from the whole using clear design objectives and constrained conditions.
- 3) Through two processes, a bottom-up process and top-down process, diverse design solutions that satisfy the design objectives and constraint conditions are derived.
- 4) Design solutions, which are similar to those derived by the emergent design system, can be derived by repeating the bottom-up and top-down processes.

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Fig. 13 Iterating the Bottom-up and Top-down Processes

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